

Customers' Perception towards the Service Marketing Mix and Frequency of Use of Mercedes Benz Automobile Service, Thailand

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Abstract : This research paper is aimed to examine a relationship between the service marketing mix and customers' frequency of use of service at Mercedes Benz Auto Repair Centres under Thonburi Group, Thailand. Based on 2,267 customers who used the service of Thonburi Group's Auto Repair Centres as the population, the sampling of this research was a total of 340 samples, by use of Probability Sampling Technique. Systematic Random Sampling was applied by use of questionnaire in collecting the data at Thonburi Group's Auto Repair Centres. Mean and Pearson's basic statistical correlations were utilized in analyzing the data. The study discovered a medium level of customers' perception towards product and service of Thonburi Group's Auto Repair Centres, price, place or distribution channel and promotion. People who provided service were perceived also at a medium level, whereas the physical evidence and service process were perceived at a high level. Furthermore, there appeared a correlation between the physical evidence and service process, and customers' frequency of use of automobile service per year.

Keywords : service marketing mix, behavior, Mercedes Auto Service Centre, frequency of use

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